

ACQUIRED IMMUNE DEFICIENCY SYNDROME

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Abstract: In this article, I would like to provide information about HIV and AIDS, their symptoms, causes, symptoms in humans, the causes of the disease and its treatment. AIDS is not only a problem of doctors and healthcare workers, but also a problem of many scientists, government officials, economists, lawyers and sociologists. Everyone should know about this disease and take precautionary measures in order to prevent the spread of AIDS for themselves and those around them.

Key words: AIDS, HIV, retrovirus, cells, antiretrovirals, symptoms, sperm, blood, infection, red rash, internal fluid, pain, chills.

AIDS (Acquired Immune Deficiency Syndrome) is a disease caused by HIV (Acquired Immune Deficiency Virus). The disease changes the human immune system, increases susceptibility to infections and other diseases. The HIV virus is found in all tissues of a person, it is transmitted through the body fluid of an infected person. For example, it has been found to spread through semen, vaginal secretions, blood and breast milk. Every person can be infected with the AIDS virus, regardless of age, gender, place of residence, social origin or other characteristics and factors. All this depends on the person's body and behavior. HIV belongs to the family of retroviruses, it damages important organs of the body and cells of the immune system. If antiretroviral therapy is not carried out against the development of the virus, the virus develops rapidly in the body. The development of the virus depends on various factors. These can be a person's age, health, other infections, genetic factors. Initial symptoms of AIDS: some people infected with HIV may not have

symptoms of the disease for months or even years. In 80% of cases, symptoms of influenza infection can be observed 2-6 weeks after being infected with the virus. This is called acute retroviral syndrome. Early symptoms of HIV include: high fever, chills, joint pain, muscle pain, sore throat, profuse night sweats, enlarged glands, red rashes on the body, fatigue, rapid weight loss. According to data, 1 out of 8 people infected with the disease do not know that they are infected with AIDS. The diagnosis of the AIDS virus is determined by a general blood test. If HIV is found, the result is positive. But the analysis is repeated. If a person is infected with the virus, it is necessary to submit an analysis as soon as possible. The earlier the diagnosis, the more effective the treatment. Testing should be done 3 to 6 months after being infected with the virus. Currently, there are no drugs against HIV and AIDS. People infected with the AIDS virus can only be helped by stopping the virus from multiplying. If a person has been infected with the virus within the last 72 hours, antiviral drugs can stop the virus from multiplying. This course of treatment must be carried out for 4 weeks.

The last period of HIV disease can take 1-5 years from the time of the virus to the time when the body cannot protect itself. It is only then that the life-threatening stage of AIDS begins. At the beginning, a person does not notice it, feels good and does not even suspect that he has been infected with the AIDS virus. It can take up to 10 years for HIV infection to progress to the stage of AIDS.

Ways of transmission of the AIDS virus:

- when infected blood is transfused into a healthy person;
- from an infected mother to a child during pregnancy, childbirth and breastfeeding;
- when using damaged syringes. There is a great risk of contracting the AIDS virus in dentistry, hairdressing salons, beauty salons (manicure, pedicure and tattoo parlors).

The AIDS virus is not transmitted in the following cases:

- when you hold hands or hug;
- when sneezing, coughing;
- when bathing in the pool;

- when using a common dish, telephone and common toilet;
- when bitten by insects.

There are 3 main ways of transmitting HIV:

1. sexual way;
2. through the blood;
3. from mother to child.

There are even medicines that stop the growth of HIV if it is suspected.

Statistics:

Currently, there are 30 million people infected with the AIDS virus. more than 6 people died from the disease. More than 8,000 people are infected with this virus per day!!!

Patients infected with the AIDS virus:

- In Africa-46.5%
- In America-33.0%
- In Europe-10.5%
- In Russia-6.0%
- In Asia-3.5%
- In Oceania-0.5%

Among those infected with the AIDS virus, the majority of children under the age of 15 is a sad case.

Conclusion: Since this infection is one of the most common diseases, protection measures should be carried out with the participation of representatives of all spheres of social life. Every young man and woman should be aware of the ways of spreading this infection, measures to prevent it and protect themselves from it.